

THE NATURAL-GEOGRAPHICAL CONDITIONS, RESOURCES, AND SETTLEMENT PATTERNS OF THE MIL-MUGAN ECONOMIC REGION

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ABSTRACT

The Mil-Mugan economic region, located in the southern part of Azerbaijan's Kura-Aras lowland, is characterized by highly favorable natural and geographical conditions. The purpose of this study is to analyze the natural-geographical features, soil and water resources, climatic conditions, ecological challenges, and their impact on settlement patterns, agriculture, and the development of social infrastructure in the region. The research is based on descriptive-geographical analysis using historical-geographical sources, ecological atlases, and statistical data. The results indicate that the relief of the Mil and Mugan plains is mostly flat and gently sloping, with most areas lying below sea level. The climate is semi-desert and arid steppe, with hot, dry summers and mild winters, necessitating extensive irrigation. The Kura and Aras rivers, along with numerous irrigation canals, play a key role in agricultural development, although they also contribute to salinization and soil degradation. The soil cover is dominated by gray-brown and saline soils, while vegetation consists mainly of wormwood-saltwort deserts, with riparian tugay forests along the Kura River. Forests in Beylagan and Sabirabad help regulate the local microclimate, whereas Saatly and Imishli districts lack significant forest resources. Findings show that natural and ecological factors directly determine settlement patterns and economic activities in the Mil-Mugan plain. Therefore, ensuring sustainable development in the region requires the preservation of ecological balance, improvement of land reclamation measures, and the promotion of renewable energy sources.

Keywords: Mil-Mugan economic region, natural-geographical conditions, climate, soil resources, ecological problems.

INTRODUCTION

Among the natural-geographical regions of Azerbaijan, the Mil-Mugan economic region stands out with its favorable climate and soil resources, playing a crucial role in the country's agricultural specialization. Situated mainly between the Kura and Aras rivers, this area has historically developed as an important center of settlement and agricultural activity. Studying the natural-geographical potential of the region is essential for understanding the development of agriculture, the formation of settlement systems, the distribution of social infrastructure, and the management of ecological challenges. Existing research highlights that climatic conditions, water resources, and soil composition directly determine the prospects of farming and livestock breeding in the area. However, the expansion of irrigation systems has led to problems such as soil salinization and land degradation, which pose risks to agricultural sustainability. For this reason, an in-depth study of the Mil-Mugan economic region is not only of scientific and geographical importance but also vital for ecological security, sustainable agriculture, and regional development policies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is based on descriptive-geographical analysis supported by statistical data, cartographic materials, and ecological atlases. Primary sources include the *Ecological Atlas of Azerbaijan (2010)*, the *Azerbaijan Geography (2015)*, and relevant volumes of the *Great Soviet*

Encyclopedia (GSE), which provide information on natural conditions, climate, soils, and hydrology. Comparative analysis was applied to identify the relationship between natural-geographical factors and settlement distribution, while synthesis methods were used to generalize ecological and socio-economic impacts. All data were systematically processed and interpreted to ensure reproducibility of results.

The Mil-Mugan economic region covers the southern part of Azerbaijan's Kura-Aras lowland and enjoys very favorable natural and geographical conditions. Most of the area lies below sea level, while the Beylagan district and the part of Imishli near the Iranian border are situated slightly above sea level. The majority of the territory belongs to the Mugan plain, with a smaller portion belonging to the Mil plain. The Mugan plain includes the right banks of the Aras and Kura rivers, whereas the Mil plain covers the area between these two rivers. The western part of Beylagan district belongs to the Karabakh and Aras lowlands. In earlier periods, the lowland was submerged by transgressive waters during the Late Pleistocene of the Quaternary period, forming bays.

The Mugan plain is the southern part of the Kura-Aras lowland. It is separated from the Mil plain to the northwest by the Aras River, and from the Shirvan and Southeastern Shirvan plains to the north and northeast by the Kura River. To the south and southeast, it connects with the Lankaran lowland and the Salyan plain. The southwestern part borders Iran. Most of the Mugan plain lies below sea level, with elevations reaching 40-50 meters only in the southwest. The surface is smooth and gently sloping. This area once contained the ancient riverbeds of the Kura and Aras rivers. It is composed of sandy and clayey marine and continental sediments of anthropogenic origin. [6;84]

The Mil plain is located between the Kura and Aras rivers. To the west, it is bordered by the Karabakh plain and the Aras lowlands, while to the north, the Kura River separates it from the Shirvan plain, and the Aras River separates it from the Mugan plain. The elevation rises towards the west, reaching between 50 and 100 meters, whereas the eastern part lies below sea level. The surface is smooth and gently sloping. Ancient riverbeds of the Kura and Aras, along with shallow depressions formed by lakes and swamps, can be found here. The plain is composed of sediments of anthropogenic origin. Its natural resources include oil (notably from the Muradkhanli field) and various construction materials. [6]

There are four administrative districts within the ER: Beylagan, Imishli, Saatly, and Sabirabad.

Beylagan district is located in the southwestern part of the ER, mainly situated between the Aras and Kura rivers. Most of its territory belongs to the Karabakh and Mil plains, with a smaller part belonging to the Aras lowlands. The total area is 1,131 square kilometers. The terrain is a gently sloping plain in the northeast and east, while the southern part is more uneven compared to the east, with elevations reaching 50-60 meters. In the west, the elevation rises above 100 meters.

The city of Beylagan is located on the right bank of the Khanqizi Canal. Most of the settlements are found in the northwest part of the region along the irrigation canals. Several villages are situated along the Upper Karabakh Canal. The largest villages, Mil and Muradli, lie along the lower section of the Khanqizi Canal. Most villages are located along the railway line and between it and the Aras River.

Due to unfavorable conditions such as salty soil and marshlands, there are no rural settlements north of the Imishli-Aghjabadi highway.

A large part of Imishli district covers the Mil plain, while a smaller portion lies within the Mugan plain. With an area of 1,890 square kilometers, it is the largest district within the IR region. Most of the territory is located below sea level, except for the border area along the Aras River and the edge of the Mugan plain, where elevations reach 30-40 meters. The city of Imishli is situated in the center of the district, between the main railway line and the Aras River.

The Bilesuvar-Imishli-Kurdamir highway also passes through here. Most villages, along with the settlement of Bahramtepe, are located along the Aras lowlands.

In 2010, several villages in Imishli district suffered severe damage due to flooding caused by the overflow of the Kura River, forcing residents to relocate. One of the most affected villages was Allahmedli. Since the village was submerged, the residents were moved to a newly established settlement near Telishli village.

Saatli district spans both the Mil and Mugan plains, with the majority of its territory in the Mugan plain. The entire area lies below sea level and covers 1,180.5 square kilometers. Elevation rises gradually from -20 meters in the west to -10 meters in the east. The district center is located in the northern part of the territory on the right bank of the Aras River, along the southern railway line. Settlements are found on both the right and left banks of the Aras River and along the Sabir canal, while other villages lie in the northern part of the Mugan plain near canals, irrigation ditches, and the new branch of the Aras River (such as Gazanbatan and Shirinbeyli).

Sabirabad district covers mostly the Mugan plain, with a smaller part in the Shirvan plain, and has an area of 1,469 square kilometers, making it the second-largest district in the IR region. Most of its territory lies below sea level, with the lower right bank of the Kura River at an elevation of -20 to -21 meters, an area notable for its rural settlements. The majority of villages are located in the northern part of the district, along both banks of the Kura River. The district center is in the northwest, on the right bank of the Aras River, near the confluence of two rivers. Less populated areas include much of the Shirvan plain as well as the southern parts of the Mugan plain. Villages are more densely settled along the Sabir (Lenin) canal.

Graphic 1.

The Mil-Mugan economic region is characterized by a semi-desert and dry steppe climate, with mild winters and hot, dry summers. In terms of sunshine duration, this area ranks third in Azerbaijan after the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and the Absheron region, with

annual sunshine hours ranging between 2,200 and 2,400. Around 40-45% of these sunshine hours occur during the summer months. The average temperature in January ranges from 0 to 3°C, while in July it ranges from 25 to 27°C. Monthly and annual average temperatures vary unevenly across the region. For example, the average annual temperature is 13.8°C in Beylagan and 14.2°C in Sabirabad. In January, average temperatures vary from 1.0 to 3.0°C, with higher temperatures observed in the eastern part of the region (around 3.0°C). In Sabirabad, the average January temperature is 1.2°C. The frost-free period lasts on average between 235 and 260 days. Maximum air temperatures occur in July and August, reaching around 40°C, while absolute minimum temperatures range from -1°C to -26°C. The highest recorded temperature in Sabirabad is +42°C, and the lowest is -23°C. [2;20]

The average annual temperature along the Kura River bank in the Mugan plain is about 14°C. According to agro-climatic zones, the central and northern parts of the Mugan plain in the IR are classified as dry and hot, the southern and border areas as semi-dry and hot, while the Mil plain is categorized as semi-dry and hot as well. [2;25]

Due to the low humidity levels in the ER, continuous irrigation is necessary, which has led to the construction of many canals and irrigation ditches.

Soil surface temperature studies also play a crucial role in organizing agricultural production. In the Kura-Aras lowland, soil temperature varies unevenly depending on soil type and vegetation. The lowest soil surface temperatures occur in January, ranging from 1°C to 3.5°C. In the western part of the lowland, the average monthly soil surface temperature in January is -1.3°C, while in the east it reaches 3.4°C. The highest soil surface temperatures are observed in July, ranging between 32°C and 35°C, which favors autumn sowing. Soil surface temperatures peak around 1 PM, reaching 7-11°C in January and 50-57°C in July. Because of these high temperatures, working in the fields between 11 AM and 5 PM is not recommended.

Local winds are common in the Mil-Mugan plains, including the white wind (ağ yel), black wind (qara yel), and boğanag (a type of dry wind). In summer, eastern and southeastern winds dominate, while in winter, western and northwestern winds prevail. The average annual wind speed increases from west to east. At the end of spring and during summer, dry and hot white winds are frequent. When persistent, these winds can cause significant damage to agriculture. They mainly blow from the south and southeast. During these winds, temperatures can rise to 40°C, while relative humidity drops to 20-25%. [1]

Annual precipitation ranges between 200 and 300 mm. Precipitation decreases from west to east, especially noticeable during the summer months. The highest rainfall occurs in the Aras lowlands of Beylagan and Imishli districts. Rainfall peaks in November and April, while the driest periods, with minimal rainfall (1 mm or less), occur during July and August. In the central and eastern parts, the number of dry days reaches 60-70, and in foothill areas, 80-90. Days with rainfall over 30 mm are rare, averaging 0.5 days on the right bank of the Kura River and 1 day in the central region.

Annual potential evaporation in the ER ranges from 1,000 to 1,150 mm. The irrigation requirements during the warm season are closely related to the amount of potential evaporation. During the warm period, potential evaporation ranges between 700 and 900 mm, and during the cold period, between 200 and 260 mm.

Surface Water: The main water arteries in the region are the Kura and Aras rivers, along with the irrigation canals connected to them. Due to the flat terrain, conditions for water flow formation are quite unfavorable, which also causes difficulties in the operation of the canal and collector-drainage systems. Along the modern course of the Kura River, there are lakes (Mehman and Sarisu) and marshlands. Mehman Lake is located in Beylagan district, while Sarisu is in Imishli district, both surrounded by extensive marshy areas. To regulate these territories, the Mil-Mugan collector canal was constructed.

Numerous meanders are found along the Kura riverbank within the ER. A significant part of the region's hydrography is influenced by the Upper Karabakh irrigation canal, which branches off from the southern part of the Mingachevir reservoir, as well as smaller canals like Bash Mugan and Resularkh, which branch from the Aras River. The Resularkh canal runs along the left bank of the Aras. During the irrigation season, 45 cubic meters per second of water is released from the Upper Karabakh canal into the Aras River. This water is then diverted through the Bahramtepe water junction into canals that irrigate the Mugan areas of the Kura-Aras lowland.

It is important to note that before the New Khanqizi canal was put into operation, groundwater levels in non-irrigated areas were 10-20 meters below the surface. After irrigation began, the groundwater level rose closer to the surface, causing soil salinization in some parts and waterlogging in others.

In addition to canals, the ER includes numerous collectors and irrigation ditches in all administrative districts. More than half of the land in each district is irrigated. In Beylagan district, the area of newly irrigated land has doubled. [2;88]

Artesian Waters: Artesian waters are more commonly found in the Aras River's alluvial plains. The alluvial cones of the Khachinchay and Qarqar rivers cover more than half of the Mil plain. Currently, artesian waters are widely used throughout the region, with Beylagan district being particularly notable. The water from these artesian wells is used both for drinking water supply and irrigation purposes.

Soils: Gray-brown soils are one of the most widespread soil types in the region, forming large masses across the Mil and Mugan plains. The development of these soils is significantly influenced by groundwater and surface water. Processes such as gleying, salinization, and desertification characterize these soils. Gray-brown soils pose considerable challenges for agricultural development because they contain relatively low amounts of humus, ranging between 2.0% and 3.5%.

Gray-marsh soils are more commonly formed along the right bank of the Kura River. Within the region, these soils are found on the Mil, Mugan, and Karabakh plains. Floodwaters, drainage waters, and groundwater have played a major role in their formation.

Saline soils are primarily found on the Mil plain near the Kura River and in Sabirabad district along the right bank of the Kura. Nearly 40% of the region's land consists of moderately to severely saline soils. Soil salinity increases from west to east. Chloride salines are widespread in the Mugan plain, while sulfate salines are common in the Mugan and Karabakh plains. Soda-affected saline soils are found in the Arazboi lowlands.

Vegetation: The Mil-Mugan plains are characterized by widespread wormwood-saltwort deserts, represented in various forms such as wormwood-horseweed and wormwood-kipchak variants. Saltwort and wormwood-saltwort deserts serve as important winter pastures for livestock farming. Wormwood semi-deserts are used as grazing lands and can also be harvested for hay.

Wetland vegetation is found along the slow-flowing Mehman and Sarisu lakes and the low-lying areas along the right bank of the Kura River. The most common type of wetland vegetation is reed thickets, which cover large areas around Sarisu and Mehman lakes. Reed beds are also found along the Kura lowlands, the Aras River banks, and on the Karabakh and Mil plains. These reed thickets typically form one or two layers and can grow densely up to 4-5 meters in height, limiting the growth of other plant species.

Forest Cover: Tugai forests grow along the Kura River, especially evident in the Mil plain area. Forest cover is mainly distributed in Beylagan and Sabirabad districts, while it is sparse in Saatli and Imishli districts. In the latter two districts, newly planted forest areas are notable.

Table 1

Distribution of main tree species in the forests along the banks of the Kura River, ha

Forestry	Total area	Forest-covered area	Dominant tree species in the forest					
			White poplar	Willow	Oak	Elm	Mulberry	Tamarisk
Beylagan	4790	3005	107	461	86	157	66	945
Sabirabad	8006	3387	164	1057	-	141	36	1763
Total:	12796	6392	271	1518	86	298	102	2708

Source: *Geography of Azerbaijan, Volume III*. Baku: Elm və Təhsil Publishing House, 2015, p. 254, Table 6.1.

Beylagan and Sabirabad districts, despite being located in the Aran region, differ in terms of forestry. Both districts mainly consist of riparian tugay forests along riverbanks, which are home to plant species sensitive to human activities. In Sabirabad, the proportion of forested areas relative to the total land is slightly higher compared to Beylagan. Willow and bulrush trees dominate these forests, which is a distinctive feature of the tugay ecosystem along the Kura River. Valuable tree species such as oak and elm are more widespread in Sabirabad, likely due to more favorable soil and water conditions. In contrast, Beylagan has a greater presence of white poplar and mulberry trees, possibly influenced by its proximity to agricultural lands and agroforestry practices.

The natural and ecological characteristics of the Mil-Mugan economic region—especially the scarcity of forest cover, the predominance of irrigated lands, and the semi-desert climate—directly affect settlement patterns and the development of social infrastructure. Since the terrain is mostly flat and gently sloping, building extensive irrigation systems has been relatively easy, encouraging agricultural settlement. Population density is higher near irrigated lands, and settlements tend to cluster around canals, ditches, reservoirs, and artesian wells.

The forests in Beylagan and Sabirabad help moderate the local microclimate, creating more favorable conditions for agriculture, which in turn supports higher population density. In contrast, areas like Saatli and Imishli, where forest cover is minimal, experience harsher climates, saltier soils, and greater risks of waterlogging, resulting in sparser and more scattered settlements.

The expansion of irrigation has increased cultivated areas, requiring the development of agricultural infrastructure such as pumping stations, collector-drainage systems, and water distribution networks. However, the rise in soil salinity and waterlogging has caused land degradation, drinking water shortages, and higher infrastructure costs in some settlements.

Thus, the geographical and ecological factors in the Mil-Mugan plain shape not only the natural landscape but also the planning and dynamics of settlement and social infrastructure development. Historically, proximity to water bodies has greatly influenced settlement locations, from ancient times to the mid-20th century, when collective farms and state farms were established around irrigation canals.

Villages mainly cluster along the fertile banks of the Araz and Kura Rivers. In Imishli and Saatli, settlements are found along both banks of the Araz River, while in Sabirabad, they are concentrated along both sides of the Kura River. Studies show that rural settlements in the Mil-Mugan economic region tend to be compact and closely linked to natural irrigation systems such as the Basqarabag and Mil-Mugan canals.

In Beylagan, villages near the border have strategic importance for sustainable development in the country.

Since the region is a plain, villages are mostly located at low elevations, often below sea level. Out of 516 villages nationwide, 137, with a population of around 221,700 out of

803,700 people, are situated in the Mil-Mugan economic region. About 72% of the villages and 68% of the population in these districts live at this low elevation level. In Sabirabad and Saatli, all villages and residents are at this altitude, while in Imishli, 42% of villages and 30% of the rural population reside there.

The second most populated elevation zone, up to 100 meters above sea level, hosts all villages and residents in Beylagan and 70% of the rural population in Imishli.

The region holds significant potential for renewable energy development, including solar, wind, and hydro energy sources. Developing these could provide electricity to rural areas, create jobs, and contribute to regional economic growth.

Mil-Mugan also has rich natural and cultural heritage, offering great opportunities for tourism development. Promoting tourism infrastructure and ecotourism—especially in areas like Ag Gol National Park and Sarisu Lake—could generate employment and boost the economy.

The region is ecologically sensitive, so environmental protection must be a priority in all development activities. The government should promote sustainable land use practices, protect natural habitats, and improve waste management systems in the area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The findings of the study demonstrate that the Mil-Mugan economic region is defined by a unique combination of natural and geographical conditions, which directly shape agricultural development, settlement distribution, and ecological stability. The relief of the Mil and Mugan plains, mostly lying below sea level, provides favorable grounds for irrigation-based farming; however, it simultaneously increases the risks of waterlogging and soil salinization. The semi-desert climate, with hot, dry summers and mild winters, makes agriculture highly dependent on the irrigation network formed by the Kura and Aras rivers and their canals.

Analysis of soil composition shows that gray-brown and saline soils dominate, containing low levels of humus (2–3.5%), which limits fertility. As a result, large-scale land reclamation and melioration measures are required to ensure sustainable agricultural productivity. Vegetation is largely characterized by wormwood-saltwort semi-deserts, while tugay forests along the Kura River provide essential ecological services, such as regulating the microclimate and protecting biodiversity. The comparative analysis between districts revealed that Beylagan and Sabirabad benefit from a higher share of riparian forests, which improves local climatic conditions and supports agricultural resilience, whereas Saatly and Imishli are more vulnerable to ecological stress due to limited forest resources and high salinity.

The study further indicates that settlement patterns are strongly linked to natural water resources, with villages clustering along canals, rivers, and artesian wells. However, anthropogenic impacts, including extensive irrigation and land use, have accelerated ecological degradation. This highlights the urgent need for integrated land management strategies, the promotion of renewable energy sources, and the development of eco-tourism to ensure long-term socio-economic and environmental sustainability in the Mil-Mugan economic region.

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MİL-MUĞAN İQTİSADI RAYONUNUN TƏBİİ-COĞRAFI ŞƏRAİTİ, EHTİYATLARI VƏ MƏSKUNLAŞMA XÜSUSİYYƏTLƏRİ

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XÜLASƏ

Azərbaycanın cənubunda, Kür-Araz ovalığının bir hissəsində yerləşən Mil-Muğan iqtisadi rayonu əlverişli təbii-coğrafi şəraitə malikdir. Bu tədqiqatın məqsədi regionun təbii-coğrafi xüsusiyyətlərini, torpaq və su ehtiyatlarını, iqlim şəraitini, ekoloji problemləri və onların əhali məskunlaşmasına, kənd təsərrüfatına və sosial infrastrukturun inkişafına təsirini təhlil etməkdir. Tədqiqat təsviri-coğrafi analizə əsaslanaraq tarixi-coğrafi mənbələr, ekoloji atlaslar və statistik məlumatlar əsasında aparılmışdır. Nəticələr göstərir ki, Mil və Muğan düzənliklərinin relyefi əsasən düz və az mailidir, ərəzilərin böyük hissəsi dəniz səviyyəsindən aşağıda yerləşir. İqlim yarımsəhra və quraq bozqır tipindədir – yaylar isti və quraq, qışlar isə mülayim keçir, bu isə genişmiqyaslı suvarmanı zəruri edir. Kənd təsərrüfatının inkişafında Kür və Araz çayları, eləcə də çoxsaylı suvarma kanalları mühüm rol oynayır, lakin eyni zamanda torpaqların şoranlaşmasına və deqradasiyasına səbəb olur. Torpaq örtüyündə əsasən boz-qonur və şorakət torpaqlar üstünlük təşkil edir. Bitki örtüyü əsasən yovşan-şoranotlu səhralardan ibarətdir, Kür çayı boyunca isə çökəkliklərdə tuqay meşələrinə rast gəlinir. Beyləqan və Sabirabad rayonlarındakı meşəliklər mikroiklimin tənzimlənməsində mühüm rol oynayır, lakin Saatlı və İmişli rayonlarında meşə ehtiyatları yetərinə inkişaf etməmişdir. Tədqiqat nəticələri göstərir ki, təbii və ekoloji amillər Mil-Muğan düzənliyində məskunlaşma və təsərrüfat fəaliyyətlərini birbaşa müəyyənləşdirir. Buna görə də regionda dayanıqlı inkişafın təmin edilməsi ekoloji tarazlığın qorunması, meliorativ tədbirlərin tətbiq edilməsi və bərpa olunan enerji mənbələrinin təşviq edilməsini tələb edir.

Açar sözlər: Mil-Muğan iqtisadi rayonu, təbii-coğrafi şərait, iqlim, torpaq ehtiyatları, ekoloji problemlər.

ПРИРОДНО-ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ, РЕСУРСЫ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАССЕЛЕНИЯ МИЛЬ- МУГАНСКОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЙОНА

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РЕЗЮМЕ

Миль-Муганский экономический район, расположенный на юге Азербайджана в пределах Кура-Аразской низменности, характеризуется благоприятными природно-географическими условиями. Цель данного исследования — проанализировать природно-географические особенности, почвенно-водные ресурсы, климатические условия, экологические проблемы и их влияние на расселение населения, сельское хозяйство и развитие социальной инфраструктуры региона. Работа основана на описательно-географическом анализе с использованием историко-географических

источников, экологических атласов и статистических данных. Результаты показывают, что рельеф Мильской и Муганской равнин преимущественно равнинный и слабо наклонный, при этом большая часть территории расположена ниже уровня моря. Климат засушливый, полупустынно-степной — с жарким, сухим летом и мягкой зимой, что требует широкомасштабного орошения. Реки Кура и Араз, а также многочисленные оросительные каналы играют ключевую роль в развитии сельского хозяйства, однако способствуют засолению и деградации почв. Почвенный покров представлен в основном серо-бурыми и засоленными почвами. Растительность включает в себя полынно-солянковые пустыни, а вдоль реки Кура сохраняются пойменные тугайные леса. Лесные массивы в Бейлагане и Сабирабаде способствуют регулированию местного микроклимата, тогда как в Саатлинском и Имишлинском районах лесные ресурсы развиты слабо. Исследование показывает, что природные и экологические факторы напрямую определяют особенности расселения и хозяйственной деятельности на Миль-Муганской равнине. Поэтому обеспечение устойчивого развития региона требует сохранения экологического баланса, улучшения мелиорационных мероприятий и продвижения возобновляемых источников энергии.

Ключевые слова: Миль-Муганский экономический район, природно-географические условия, климат, почвенные ресурсы, экологические проблемы.